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Description of the Improvement of Pedagogical Technologies for the Use of Oratory in the Process of Spiritual and Educational Work

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***Annotation:** this scholarly article states that the social adaptation of each individual is achieved through communication. Now, a student entering a higher education institution experiences a process of maladaptation. That is, it is a little difficult to find friends, to communicate with fellow students and teachers. If a student has developed oratory skills, they quickly adapt to the team and take initiative.*

***Key words:** communication, beautiful speech, intellect, sincerity, imagination, worldview.*

This shows that strengthening students' communication plays a special role in the formation of oratory. Communication is an important form of interaction, reflecting a person's inner and outer world. In the process of constant communication, people reflect their views, imaginations, and feelings about the external world, the way of life of society, its social, economic, and spiritual life. As social relations between members of society and living conditions change, their perceptions, concepts, worldviews, morals, and norms of morality about the material world also change. Such a change occurs on the basis of common interests and goodwill of people. With the emergence of human society, there was a need for communication between people. The first factor in students' sociability is empathy. It takes place in the process of developing the ability to understand the feelings of another person, to approve of the point of view of others, and to normalize relationships within the collective. Communication is one of the needs of people arising in the process of their joint activities in a particular group or group, and it is a process of entering into mutual relationships during their activities. People have their own "I" at work, in transportation, at home, in general, so we need to know who and how to communicate. How knowledgeable and intelligent a person is is manifested through their communication. People convey and realize their entire inner world, purpose, behavior, and relationships to each other through words. Therefore, communication between people should be pleasant. People like and respect such people. Communication is also a kind of art. A thorough study of this art is necessary for every person. At the same time, the perfect study of the native language is a sacred duty of every person. Having learned a

language, it is necessary for a person to master the art of using it. In the process of communication, sweetness and beautiful speech are never sold anywhere. There is only one way to achieve this. And that's the practice of talking all the time.

This is mainly done by reading a lot of books. Behavior is the face that reveals who a person is. Research shows that the speaker's positive attitude towards the listener, addressing them in a clear, calm tone, helps them feel free. If we define communication, it is a form of conversation, conversation, interpersonal conversation and exchange of ideas, oral speech, in which two or more people speak. Communication is one of the characteristics unique to humans. People have a desire to say something to each other in the process of activity. Communication is typically a multifaceted process of developing connections between people, arising from the needs of joint activity. Communicativeness is a quality that involves actively exchanging information between collaborators. The communicative aspect of the relationship is taken into account in this process. When people engage in communication, they first turn to language. Another aspect of interpersonal communication is the mutual interaction of the interlocutors in the process of speech, not only by words, but also by actions. For example, when we engage in a relationship, we interact with gestures if they satisfy us. Another aspect is that it is important for those entering into communication to feel each other in social relationships. For example, we treat a person with respect or disdain before we interact with them. It is during communication that we observe his behavior, and due to his behavior and so on, our opinion of our interlocutor changes in some way. Therefore, communication is one of the important aspects of humanity, and human communication culture ensures the emergence of negative and positive thoughts in people. Communicative etiquette is a process that leads a person to spiritual perfection. Communicative etiquette is formed from childhood. As a child grows, the level of communication etiquette expands. Communicative etiquette is a process that determines a person's activity and protects them from all mistakes. As a result, her moral beauty increases. The development of students' communication motivation based on collaboration is primarily manifested as a result of changing their communication motivation. In this case, collaborative learning involves training each student in intensive daily mental work, fostering awareness and independence as an individual, fostering a sense of personal dignity in each student, strengthening confidence in one's own strength and abilities, and fostering a sense of responsibility in learning. This requires the development of communication motivation based on collaboration. Communication and speech are one of the processes inherent only to humans.

People need to communicate with each other in the process of their activities. Communication, naturally, is considered the most important sign of the emergence of human society. The development of collaboration technology and communication motivation in students liberates them from various factors influencing their development and creates conditions for friendly, free communication between students and faculty. The importance of the formed qualities and qualities of a person is extremely important in the successful communication between people. In particular, if a person has well-developed positive qualities (kindness, modesty, humanity, correctness, honesty, etc.), the communication process ends positively. Because in order for people to understand each other correctly, for communication to be successful, it is desirable that they be sincere. Sincerity among people is one of the most beautiful human qualities, a rational attitude towards events and events, not succumbing to various influences. One way to teach students to communicate is to develop communication skills in the form of classes. In youth, a person should be trained in communication through socio-psychological trainings. People themselves should react positively to these methods and take active action. After all, without communication, a person does not fully develop either as a subject of activity or as an individual. Today, the foundation of the educational process is the issue of teaching

communication. Students always feel the need for communication during their studies. The educational significance of interpersonal communication lies in its expansion of a person's worldview and the formation of their psyche. In other words, all mental processes develop through communication. The second direction in shaping the student's collective environment is the formation of the spiritual culture of team members. Therefore, it is important to provide students with information that stimulates their reflections on human communication, human personality, and the characteristics of mutual evaluation. Students can be taught methods of communication through various creative essays, open roundtables, trainings, and special exercises. As a means of communication, we can mention speech (oral and written), paralinguistic (sound tone, speed of speech, voice timbre), kinesic (behavior, facial expressions, other forms of movement) and object-marked (sculpture, pictures) means of communication. Every era has its own ideas and forms. As long as religious and secular teachings have their influence on human perfection, preaching has the right to live in a new way. And the culture of communication is an integral part of it. It is true that a spiritually enlightened society has used immortal ideas and forms.

It is appropriate to consider that the interaction with the community has a social essence. The presentation of festive events, creative evenings, concert programs, or wedding ceremonies is also a reflection of the culture of communication with the collective as a propagandist of spirituality. Failure to know the specific requirements of this leads to paralysis, speech defects, and uncomfortable situations in the process of communication. According to renowned scholar N.P. Anikeyeva, in communication with other people, each individual plays a specific social role. Roles are usually more likely to reveal the nature of a person or to mask it. However, it should be said that the choice of position, i.e., social roles, will inevitably depend on a person's essence, their strength, weakness, level of potential, ability to self-criticise, the sophistication of their behavior, and the ability to see themselves from the outside. Failure in communication sometimes encourages students to hide their best qualities in order to be more flawless and protected. The psychological characteristics inherent in all people are determined by the type of nervous system. It is primarily manifested in temperament, impact rate, natural signals (voice, light, color, smell, temperature change), social signals (word, event, hypersensitivity, emotional excitability, anxiety level, extraversion, introversion). In psychology, both extroversion and introversion, as we all know, are vividly reflected in the sphere of communication as a mental characteristic of a person.

Extroversion is the individual's view of the external world, while introversion is the inner world. People with extroversion characteristics associated with a strong type of nervous activity are more sociable, able to communicate freely in terms of contacts and acquaintances. Students are eager to make new acquaintances, they love noisy circles. Introverts are people who belong to a weak type of nervous activity. They tend to be absorbed in their inner worlds and experiences. They are usually worried about others. Introverts prefer a narrow circle of loved ones. From this perspective, people located in the middle of the "Extroversion-Introversion" axis are called centroverts in psychology. They are moderately sociable and moderately lonely. They can also be trained in communication by working with speech. For example, trainings like reading a poem or telling a story aloud also contribute to the formation of communication. One of the components of personality development in higher education is the culture of communication among students. In higher education, communication culture is one of the most important resources for developing a specialist in the intellectual field and a person who can creatively approach education. Developing a culture of communication allows a higher education student to acquire universal characteristics, meet societal demands, and acquire high professional knowledge. L.N. Kulikova, A.V. Molozhvenko, and V.N. Myashichev, in their works, highly valued the importance of communication in the development of the student's personality.

Psychologists asked the following questions to determine a person's ability to communicate. "Why communicate?" As a result of long scientific observations, this question was answered as follows: "Communication forms commonalities between people, guiding their joint activities." It manifests itself as a method of cognition. It serves as the primary means of knowing individuals. In this way, communication serves the self-identification of the individual, ensuring their entry into joint activities and creating an atmosphere of mutual cooperation between the subjects of communication. Before answering the question why we should engage in communication, we should not forget that there are habits, needs, and skills that we engage in communication. As a person adapts to different commonalities in this process, he manifests himself as an object and subject of communication. In the process of communication, a person feels a certain influence from those around them. In turn, he himself has a certain influence on them in the process of communication. Communication is a human need as a social, conscious being. Communication can be defined as the exchange of information between two or more people. Communication occupies a leading position among the activities that people carry out and serves to fulfill the most important human needs. For this reason, its place in the life of every person is important. All activities performed by an individual in society include forms of interaction and interaction. After all, any work requires people to find common ground with each other, to transfer different information to each other, and to exchange ideas. Therefore, the place of each individual in society, the success of their work, and their reputation are directly linked to their ability to engage in communication. This seemingly simple interpersonal communication is actually a very complex process, to which a person adapts throughout their life. The implementation of interpersonal communication functions depends on the following aspects:

It is explained by the spiritual and moral instructions of the subject of communication, as well as directions such as humanity, emotional-positive, personal approach, individuality and originality. The function of communication between people depends not only on the spiritual and moral orientation of the subjects of communication, but also largely on its humanistic and moral content. Typically, the form of communication is instantaneous, random, thematic, and planned.

It consists of describing the event, information, message, conversation, conversation, conversation, discussion, etc. In the conversation, attention, interest, approval, empathy, influence with the help of foresight, activity based on understood and realized motivation, entering the type of communication and directing it to solve the problem, creating an emotional environment, encouraging, directing it to the conclusion of joint actions, as well as the effectiveness of communication, its positive motivation, attention, interest in the topic. In psychological science, motivation as a manager of the communication process requires meaning, awareness, trust, and persistence. To the meaningful aspects of communication between people, it is important to show their individuality in achieving goals and commonalities, as well as to use various functions of communication.

Exciters can include expressive, organizational, informative, emotional, evidence-based, and others. In face-to-face interpersonal communication, the process of a person's potential-personal, professional needs, and practical perception takes place. The concept of communication and activity is viewed as a specific form of social activity and at the same time as individual independence. It is precisely the ability to pose a problem in the desired situation, its purpose, task, issues, situation and conditions of communication, factors, elements of the environment, and demand for the subject of communication that are important. At the same time, it is appropriate to emphasize the need to respect the dignity of another person in the process of communication, to adhere to simple rules of etiquette, morality, and etiquette developed by humanity. In addition, emotional-positive factors, sympathy, and empathy play an important role in communication. Words, speech, storytelling, informing, speaking, knowing how

to lead a conversation, paying attention, attention, understanding and respecting the partner, and being able to give an additional meaning to the thought with facial expressions are of great importance. Communication between people should be at the level of spiritual humanity and high etiquette. The main thing is to be able to put oneself in the place of the interlocutor in interpersonal communication. To develop an interpersonal oratory culture, it is necessary to learn to feel the mood and state of the interlocutor. Among the elements included in the process of interpersonal communication, it determines the tone of voice, facial expression, movements, gaze, positive or negative distance between the interlocutors. Because of these factors, we can conclude about the psyche, emotional state, or intentions of another person. Interpersonal communication is considered interconnected, possessing the characteristics of mutual understanding, perception, information exchange, training, development, upbringing, self-expression, self-actualization, and influence through social interaction. Humanism is understood as a set of views expressing respect for human rights and dignity, value as an individual, care for their well-being, comprehensive development, and the creation of favorable conditions for their lives. The aspect of humanizing interpersonal communication involves activating the intellectual and spiritual potential of interlocutors and realizing their personal social identity. In such communication, the student's personality is formed. Because in this process, their inner potential and personal humanity are fully manifested. Here, future specialists will demonstrate their knowledge of personality, human and human qualities, as well as the art of public speaking and the culture of communication. Humanistic communication is an important condition for future specialists to realize humanitarian ideas and values in various spheres of their personal, social, life, and professional activities. The humanitarian aspects of communication are based on a spiritual and practical foundation, that is, on morality. Ideas, ideals, and rules developed in the process of human social life and reflected in moral categories justify normative morality. The humanization of interpersonal communication is based on the following principles:

- the main thing in communication is a person,
- the main thing in communication is to communicate humanely,
- friendship, sincerity, harmony, harmony.

In this dialogue, the interlocutor must find a way, means, methods, and forms in which he feels himself not as an object, but as an equal participant in the dialogue. The communication process should be free, natural, interesting, mutually enriching, influencing, and self-expressive. In the process of communication, attention is paid to the interlocutor's personality, friendly conversation, corresponding to the conditions of communication, and the rhetorical aspect of the conversation is provided. The interlocutor demonstrates moral, ethical, and spiritual qualities. It awakens the desired feelings in the interlocutor and creates desired thoughts and comments. To purposefully influence the partner, communication is carried out on a subject-object basis, on a productive creative basis in a humanized context. Humanism in communication is the consideration of the interlocutor not as an object of interaction, but as an object of self-expression. The development of communication culture and the art of oratory among students is one of the issues that should be at the center of attention today. To successfully solve this problem, it is important to use methods that accelerate students' learning and cognitive activity, pedagogical technologies, oratory-developing games, various exercises and psychological trainings that eliminate anxiety and fear. Such trainings and methods are extremely numerous and diverse. These include, first and foremost, psychological trainings, energy-based methods, problem-communicative assignments, cognitive research projects, educational discussions, and dialogues. Didactic games also play a special role in shaping students' communication culture. Our observations show that we need to use these methods sufficiently in the formation of students'

communicative culture. The interest in using these methods and trainings in the educational process is increasing every day. This, in turn, is explained by the expansion of the scope of information and the expansion of tasks related to the orientation of the educational process towards the student's personality. It is necessary to develop students' communication skills and speaking skills, while there is also a need to develop their creative use and the need for students to learn. The use of psychodrama, that is, theatrical lessons, which is one of the methods of psychological training in the formation of the art of oratory among students, is of particular importance. The effectiveness of using theatrical lessons in the formation of oratory skills in students is clearly manifested in the following: The main scale and direction of interest in theater is that it is always built on the basis of human and human-world relations. Because this very foundation can be understood through theatrical works in the form of a game. Subsequently, due to the demands of their professional activities, students will always work in an atmosphere of interaction and collaboration when they become teachers in the future. Sometimes he establishes a business dialogue with students, sometimes with colleagues. These relationships are especially vividly expressed in the example of the heroes of the work of art. This does not mean that conducting lessons in a game only increases students' oratory skills. Game activities or trainings in classes create a process of mutually positive communication between students. This process, of course, serves as a reason and impetus for the development of students' oratory skills. In preparing students for the use of oratory in the process of spiritual and educational work, it is also important to study their psychological portraits, temperament, and character traits. Each student's individual characteristics are different, their motives, i.e., the forces driving them to action, are also different. Therefore, it is advisable to use all types of exercises and trainings aimed at developing the art of oratory. In addition to many methods, question-and-answer, conversation, and pedagogical technologies are also important in shaping the oratory skills of students.

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